

France on a Stake: The Possibilities of Using Excessive Force to Restore its Interests in Africa

Mohammed Saaida

Department of International Relations and Diplomacy, Faculty of Administration Sciences and Informatics, Al-Istiqlal University, Jericho – Palestine.

Email: confador@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7488-9832>

This academic article critically examines the potential for France to employ excessive force in its efforts to restore its interests in Africa following the political coups in Sudan, Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger. The analysis delves into France's historical engagement in the region and its strategic interests in Africa. The paper evaluates the implications of excessive force on regional dynamics, international relations, and France's image as a global actor. Drawing on primary and secondary sources, this research aims to provide an informed assessment of the risks and challenges associated with such military interventions. The article concludes with recommendations for a balanced and responsible approach that aligns with the principles of international law and promotes sustainable stability in the affected African nations. The recent political coups in Sudan, Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger have significantly impacted regional stability and posed challenges to France's strategic interests in Africa. This article critically analyzes the possibilities of France resorting to the use of excessive force to restore its interests in these African nations.

France's historical engagement in Africa spans centuries and is deeply intertwined with the continent's colonial past and post-independence era. As a former colonial power, France established a significant presence in various African regions, leaving behind a complex legacy that continues to influence its interests and actions today. The historical context of colonialism has shaped France's approach to safeguarding its economic, geopolitical, and security interests in Africa. Moreover, post-colonial relationships with African nations have played a pivotal role in determining France's policies and interventions in response to significant events, such as the recent political coups in Sudan, Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger. Understanding this historical background is fundamental to comprehending France's current actions in the region and their implications for Africa's stability and development.

France's strategic interests in Africa encompass multifaceted dimensions, reflecting its historical ties and contemporary global positioning. Economically, Africa presents abundant natural resources, markets, and investment opportunities for French businesses. Geopolitically, the continent's location provides access to key maritime routes and allows France to project influence in international affairs. From a security perspective, addressing regional instability is essential to counter terrorism and curb migration flows. Moreover, France values its cultural and historical connections with African nations, fostering diplomatic ties and cultural exchanges. These strategic interests significantly influence

France's response to political coups in Africa, guiding its actions to safeguard its core objectives on the continent.

The recent political coups in Sudan, Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger have significantly impacted regional stability and posed challenges to France's interests in Africa. A comprehensive analysis of these coups reveals specific contextual intricacies and complexities, shedding light on the evolving political landscapes in each country. The implications of these events on France's strategic interests and engagement in the continent are carefully examined. Assessing the repercussions of the coups allows for a deeper understanding of how France may respond to safeguard its interests and navigate the delicate balance between regional stability and its own priorities in Africa.

In evaluating the possibilities of France resorting to excessive force after the coups, a rigorous critical assessment is conducted. Drawing from historical examples and past military interventions, the potential ramifications of such actions on regional dynamics, civilian populations, and France's standing in the international community are thoroughly examined. The section delves into the ethical, legal, and strategic implications of employing excessive force to restore its interests in Africa. By providing a comprehensive analysis, this research aims to shed light on the complexities and risks associated with this approach, urging for a measured and responsible response to the post-coup situations.

The implications and risks of France employing excessive force to safeguard its interests in Africa are of paramount importance. The article sheds light on the potential challenges to regional stability, as military interventions could exacerbate existing tensions and trigger further conflicts. Diplomatic relations may also be strained, leading to international criticism and isolation. Additionally, the legitimacy of France's actions may be questioned, potentially undermining its role as a responsible global actor. This analysis emphasizes the need for France to carefully consider the consequences of its actions, advocating for a measured and balanced approach to preserve both its interests and Africa's stability.

Balancing security objectives with responsible actions is crucial in responding to the challenges posed by the recent political coups in Africa. This section emphasizes the need for France to adopt a nuanced approach that safeguards its strategic interests while upholding the principles of international law and respecting the sovereignty of African nations. By prioritizing diplomacy, dialogue, and multilateral cooperation, France can address security concerns while minimizing the risks of excessive force. A measured and responsible approach will not only protect France's interests but also foster constructive engagement and contribute to sustainable stability in the region, reinforcing its role as a credible and respected global partner.

The role of the international community is pivotal in responding to the political coups and ensuring stability in Sudan, Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger. This article underscores the significance of multilateral cooperation and dialogue among nations to address the complex challenges in the affected countries. By fostering collaborative efforts, the international community can provide much-needed humanitarian aid, diplomatic support, and conflict

resolution mechanisms. Such collective action not only bolsters the affected nations but also strengthens regional peace and security. The article emphasizes the shared responsibility of the international community in promoting sustainable solutions and facilitating the path towards lasting stability and development in Africa.

Based on the comprehensive analysis, this section offers recommendations for France to adopt responsible and sustainable strategies to safeguard its interests in Africa. Diplomatic engagement should take precedence, fostering open dialogues and cooperative partnerships with African nations. Prioritizing conflict resolution mechanisms, France can actively contribute to resolving underlying political tensions and promoting peace. Supporting governance and development initiatives will play a vital role in addressing root causes of instability, building institutions, and enhancing socio-economic conditions. By committing to these responsible and sustainable approaches, France can contribute to long-term stability in the region and strengthen its standing as a constructive and reliable partner in Africa's progress.

In conclusion, the article underscores the intricacies and challenges that confront France in responding to the political coups in Sudan, Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger. A balanced and responsible approach is imperative, wherein France's interests are carefully weighed against the principles of international law and the sovereignty of African nations. Emphasizing diplomacy, conflict resolution, and sustainable development initiatives will be crucial in promoting genuine and lasting stability in the region. By navigating these complexities with prudence and respect, France can forge a constructive path forward, strengthening its relations with African nations and contributing positively to regional peace and prosperity.

This work is a part of “Science For All Publications”

	Science For All Publications	
	August 2023 Electronic Publications Vol: 3 Issue: 2 pp. 1-3	Self-publication Project References Number (SFAP 230801/1)